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Are the Director of the WHO and Political Leaders of USA, UK, Canada and other countries stating that the Scientific Researchers who went to Wuhan, China in an Investigative Mission on the origin of SARS-COV-2 are a bunch of Imbeciles?

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Abstract. There is much controversy with respect to the origin of SARS-COV-2, the etiologic agent of COVID-19 that has caused much havoc and decimations in most countries worldwide, India being the latest victim due to the incompetence of its political leaders. Having demonstrated their inabilities to control the number of recorded deaths due to the spread of SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19, the incompetent Director of the World Health Organization and the Political leaders of the so-called advanced countries, including the United States, United Kingdom and Canada, and other countries pushed to blame China for the handling of the emergence of SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19. In particular, it has been argued that SARS-COV-2 originated from a Virology Lab in Wuhan, China with no scientific evidence. Thus, a team of Scientific Researchers under the auspice of the World Health Organization was set up and travel to Wuhan, China to investigate the origin of SARS-COV-2 because it is widely held that SARS-COV-2 first appeared in Wuhan, China. It must be noted that because SARS-COV-2 was first detected and its genomic sequence

determined in Wuhan, China, it does not necessarily mean that SARS-COV-2 originated in Wuhan, China. The Team of Scientific Researchers who went to Wuhan, China concluded that "the laboratory incident hypothesis is extremely unlikely to explain the introduction of the virus into the human population . . . Therefore, it is not in the hypotheses that we will suggest for future studies". Nevertheless, the Director of the WHO, Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus who has training in Community Health and knows nothing about the Science of Viruses that infect humans or SARS-COV-2 blasted the Scientific Researchers' report by stating that the Scientific Researchers "hadn't sufficiently examined the controversial hypothesis that the virus could have leaked from the Wuhan Institute of Virology". What the incompetent and moronic Director of the WHO is essentially suggesting is that the Scientific Researchers should engage in Scientific Misconduct by making Dishonest Scientific Reporting, Data Fabrication and Data Falsification in order to come up with a report that would support the hypothesis that SARS-COV-2 escaped from the Wuhan Institute of Virology". At this point in time, it is submitted that studies to prove that SARS-COV-2 somehow escaped from the Wuhan Institute of Virus would not only be unscientific, wasteful and useless, but also politically motivated, dangerous and racist. The WHO under the directorship of Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus has wasted too much money already. The Director of the WHO, Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus and the Political leaders of the so-called advanced countries, including the United States, United Kingdom and Canada, and other countries (including India) are directly responsible for the millions of deaths due to SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19.

On or around February 28, 2021, A panel of Scientific Researchers under the auspice of the World Health Organization submitted an Official Report on the original identification of SARS-COV-2 in Wuhan, China [1-3]. Among others, the panel of Scientific Researchers concluded that "the laboratory incident hypothesis is extremely unlikely to

explain the introduction of the virus into the human population . . . Therefore, it is not in the hypotheses that we will suggest for future studies". Nevertheless, the Director of the WHO, Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus who has a Ph.D. in Community Health from the University of Nottingham, UK working on the effects of dams on malaria transmission

in the Tigray region and knows nothing about the Science of Viruses that infect humans or SARS-COV-2 blasted the Scientific Researchers' report by stating that the Scientific Researchers "hadn't sufficiently examined the controversial hypothesis that the virus could have leaked from the Wuhan Institute of Virology" and made the imbecilic statement: "I do not believe that this assessment was extensive enough . . . This requires further investigation, potentially with additional missions involving specialist experts, which I am ready to deploy" [2]. The Director of the WHO is the same person who on or around January 23, 2021 declared with the support of the WHO leadership and the United States' Department of Health and Social Services, the National Institutes of Health, the National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases, the Centers for Disease Control, and other National Agencies that COVID-19 was not a global health emergency and that there was no need to worry about COVID-19 globally [4]. On or around February 3, 2020, the Director of the WHO was still thinking that "the virus' spread outside

China was minimal and slow". It was only on or around March 19, 2020, months after SARS-COV-2 was first isolated and its sequence determined that the moronic and clownish Director of the WHO (Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus declared that the Corona Virus Disease (COVID-19) is a world-wide pandemic [4-7].

The Political Leaders of the United States, United Kingdom and Canada, and other countries [8] who have zero knowledge of any aspects of the science of Viruses that infect humans and SARS-COV-2 at the most basic level and were incompetent for failing to mount an effective response to SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19 in their respective countries with over 590,000, 125,000 and 24,000 deaths (as of May 1, 2021 and still counting!) questioned the independence of the Panel of Scientific Researchers by stating that "We voice our shared concerns that the international expert study on the source of the SARS-CoV-2 virus was significantly delayed and lacked access to complete, original data and samples" and demanding that "Scientific missions like these should be able to do their work under conditions

that produce independent and objective recommendations and findings . . . Going forward, there must now be a renewed commitment by WHO and all Member States to access, transparency, and timeliness . . . ". The Governments of the United States, United Kingdom and Canada must spend more of their time and resources investigating why they failed to mount an effective response to SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19 after they knew that SARS-COV-2 had reached their shores and was highly contagious and virulent.

The Panel of Scientific Researchers who went to Wuhan, China is by all international standards, competent practitioners of Virological Sciences have independence of mind and action and would not allow themselves to be corrupted in any way or form. What are the facts? Is there any evidence that SARS-COV-2 was present in the Wuhan Institute of Virology prior to outbreak outside? It is now well established scientifically that COVID-19 was first detected and SARS-COV-2 was first isolated from patients suffering from COVID-19 on or around December 2019 [6,7]. Since the description of COVID-19

and the isolation and characterization of SARS-COV-2 [6,7], over 590,000 USA citizens, 125,000 UK citizens and 24,000 Canadian Citizens have died (as of May 1, 2021 and still counting!) (Figure 1). Comparative studies of the IP-10000 (Total Number Individuals Infected with SARS-COV-2 per 10000 Population) and DPP-10000 (Total Number of Deaths Per 10000 Population) Numbers (Figures 2) provide a more accurate picture of failures of the Director of the WHO and governments of the United States, United Kingdom and Canada.

Are the Director of the WHO and the Political Leaders of the United States, United Kingdom and Canada, and other countries who signed the joint statement [8] stating that the Panel of Scientific Researchers who concluded that there was no evidence to support the hypothesis that SARS-COV-2 originated from the Wuhan Institute of Virology, are a bunch of imbeciles and have somehow come up with an erroneous report that was not based on scientific facts? Are the Director of the WHO and the Political Leaders of the United States, United Kingdom and Canada, and other countries who signed the joint statement

[8] also stating that the Panel of Scientific Researchers have committed Scientific Dishonest Reporting, Data Fabrication and Data Falsification. After all, the report of the Panel of Scientific Researchers must be based on scientific facts and evidence, and not on political innuendos?

What are the facts? Is there any evidence that SARS-COV-2 was present in the Wuhan Institute of Virology prior to outbreak outside? It is now well established scientifically that COVID-19 was first detected and SARS-COV-2 was first isolated from patients suffering from COVID-19 on or around December 2019 [6,7]. Since the description of COVID-19 and the isolation and characterization of SARS-COV-2 [6,7], over 590,000 USA citizens, 125,000 UK citizens and 24,000 Canadian Citizens and still counting).

Figure 1. Total number of individuals infected with SARS-COV-2 (Panel A) and Total number of deaths due SARS-COV-2 infections and COVID-19 per 10000 population (Panel B) for different countries as of May 1,

The incompetence of the Director of the WHO, Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus: The Director of the WHO, Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus is the person who on March 19, 2020 finally declared that the Corona Virus Disease (COVID-19) is a world-wide pandemic, almost two and half months after the full RNA sequence of SARS-COV-2 was first published [4-7]. The Director of the WHO, Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus is the person who stated

on or around February 3, 2020 that "widespread travel ban was not needed" and agreed with so-called top scientists of the WHO in declaring that "coronavirus has not meaningfully mutated to a more lethal and more contagious form" [9]. For him to state that he is not happy with the report of the Panel of Scientific Researchers who went to investigate the hypothesis that SARS-COV-2 may have originated from the Wuhan Institute of Virology, is not only hypocritical but also disrespectful and defamatory to the Panel of Scientific Researchers. Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus is an incompetent fool who must be fired on the spot. Through his incompetence, Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus is directly responsible for the millions of deaths (still counting!) due to SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19 in the entire world. Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus was paid to pre-empt and to combat diseases, including COVID-19 that afflict humans. It is not Rocket Science to monitor the emergence of dormant viruses that can infect humans. It is not clear whether Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus and the minions who surround him would understand the concept of Virus Latency, Dormancy and Reactivation because they were never

trained in this very important of concept of Virology Sciences.

It is not clear how Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus became the Director of the WHO with an annual budget of over 5 billion US dollars.

What does Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus know about the science of Viruses that infect Humans and SARS-COV-2-2? What does Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus know about drug development and vaccine development

for the the control of SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19. What expertise does Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus has that qualifies him for running an organization with a budget of over 5 billion US dollars. According to Wikipedia, Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus has a Ph.D. in Community Health from the University of Nottingham (UK) through the study of the effect of dams on malaria transmission on the Tigray region, a highly laughable and dubious exercise. While Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus was a Minister of Health of Ethiopia from 2005 to 2012, Ethiopia was one of poorest and most corrupt countries of the world and its annual budget for the entire government of Ethiopia was ~3.5 billion US dollars for 2005 and ~8 billion US dollars for 2012 with a population of over ~72 million [10]. In 2005, Infant Mortality Rate for Ethiopia was ~71 per 1000 while in 2012, the Infant Mortality Rate for Ethiopia was ~49 per 1000. In comparison, in 2005, the Infant Mortality Rate for South Africa was ~52 per 1000 respectively, and in 2012, the Infant Mortality Rate for South Africa was ~30 per 1000 respectively [10-12].

The incompetence of the Political and Scientific Leaders of the United States, United Kingdom and Canada, Donald Trump, Boris Johnson and Justin Trudeau: The former President of the United States, Donald Trump has blood in his hands with respect to the more that 590,000 recorded deaths due to SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19 in the United States. The United States of America occupies the top podium with respect to the total number of deaths due to SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19 (Figure 1) and is among the top with respect to IP-10000, DPI-10000 and DPP-10000 Numbers (Figure 2). Did the incompetent, uneducated, imbecilic, xenophobic and racist Donald Trump not lie to the American people when he declared that "COVID-19 was just a flu from China and that by April 2020 with the warmth of spring, SARS-COV-2 would just go away" when he knew that SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19 was not only dangerous but deadly. According to the book by Bob Woodward, the incompetent, uneducated, imbecilic, xenophobic and racist Donald Trump admitted that he preferred to "downplay the bad news" [13-18]. Where was the Editor in Chief of Science Magazine when the incompetent,

uneducated, imbecilic, xenophobic and racist Donald Trump was lying to the American people [14]. Was it not the incompetent, uneducated, imbecilic, xenophobic and racist Donald Trump who insisted on calling SARS-COV-2, the "China virus" and COVID-19, the "Chinese Flu" or Kung Flu" in order to distract the American people from his failure to come up with a credible and effective national response to SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19 [13-18]. Was it not the incompetent, uneducated, imbecilic, xenophobic and racist Donald Trump who recommended and promoted Hydroxychloroquine, Bleach and some kind of "magic light" for the treatment of SARS-COV-2 infections and COVID-19 on national TV and to the world [13-18]. The election of the incompetent, uneducated, imbecilic, xenophobic and racist Donald Trump as President of the United States of America, the torch bearer of Western Liberal Democracy and guarantor of Universal Human Rights is proof that there are major flaws that must be addressed in our system of governance and that Western Liberal Democracy is facing the grave danger of become

obsolete. (Unfortunately, in the United States of America, the "elected" government is no longer a government of the people, by the people and for the people. It is more a government of the 1%, for the 1% and by the 1%. What kind of meritocratic system of liberal democracy would allow the election of a President who is incompetent, uneducated, imbecilic, xenophobic and racist?)

The Prime Minister of the United Kingdom, Boris Johnson is no better than his master, the incompetent, uneducated, imbecilic, xenophobic and racist Donald Trump. That the Prime Minister of the United Kingdom is an incompetent, imbecile and a clown is borne out by the fact that like his master, the incompetent, uneducated, imbecilic, xenophobic and racist Donald Trump, he allowed himself to be infected with SARS-COV-2. and it was so severe that he almost died of COVID-19. How did the incompetent, imbecilic and clownish Prime Minister of the United Kingdom, Boris Johnson fail in his duty to protect the citizens of the United Kingdom? Through the advice of

his equally incompetent civil servants, so-called experts and pundits, the incompetent, imbecilic and clownish Prime Minister of the United Kingdom, Boris Johnson was under the impression that the United Kingdom could achieve the so-called Herd Immunity without an effective and safe vaccine [19]. The figures speak for themselves. The United Kingdom is the basket case of Europe with more than 127,000 deaths for a population of ~59 million (Figure 1) because of the incompetent, imbecilic and clownish Boris Johnson and his equally incompetent civil servants, so-called "experts" and pundits" [19]. It is difficult to fathom that the citizen of the UK did not revolt against the incompetent, imbecilic and clownish Boris Johnson. After refusing to wear a mask, practice social distancing, and supporting and implementing the policy of achieving so-called Herd Immunity without an effective and safe vaccine, the incompetent, imbecilic and clownish Prime Minister of the United Kingdom, Boris Johnson put all his eggs in one basket by giving his support without reservation to the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine developed by Astra-Zeneca/University of Oxford [20-22]. Whether the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine developed by Astra-Zeneca/University of Oxford is effective and safe is a question that has not been answered

yet and will be answered only in 5-6 months. It is noteworthy that the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine developed by Astra-Zeneca/University of Oxford has not been approved by the United States Federal Drug Administration (FDA) and there are many worrisome questions with respect to its clinical trial. The latest action of the government of incompetent, imbecilic and clownish Boris Johnson consisting of sending the United Kingdom Navy to the Baltic Sea and South China Sea is testament to the fact that Boris Johnson's mental capacity and acumen have been deeply affected by his encounter with SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19. The idea of the United Kingdom standing up to and possibly confronting the much superior forces of the Russian and Chinese Navy is evidence of his and his Defense Secretary' "Folie de Grandeur" and inability to comprehend that the United Kingdom is not the power it used to be in the 19th and 20th century. It is downright comical, tragic and dangerous. It is noteworthy that the former prime minister of the UK, Mrs. Margaret Thatcher who was a seasoned political leader and diplomat managed to get the UK out of Hong Kong without firing a shot and not paying one cent of compensation. Here, we have the incompetent, imbecilic and clownish doing

his best to drag the UK back to Hong Kong to the detriment of the UK's economy and security.

The Prime Minister of Canada, Justin Trudeau is another incompetent, imbecile and clown who kowtowed to the incompetent, uneducated, imbecilic, xenophobic and racist Donald Trump. Under the prime-ministership of Justin Trudeau, Canada has become the laughing stock with respect to the arrest and persecution of Meng Wenzhou, the Chief Financial Officer of Huawei. It is clear to anybody with an average intellect that the arrest of Meng Wenzhou was motivated by the failure of the United States under the incompetent and imbecilic Donald Trump to win a Trade War against China that was initiated without any well thought out plan and strategy (Donald Trump and his minions, especially the incompetent, ridiculous, clownish, racist and xenophobic Mike Pompeo must go back to school to learn about world affairs, Art of Diplomacy and the Art of War. That is if any schools will accept them as students!). It is a disgrace that Donald Trump attacked a woman and in so doing has sullied the reputation of the United States (If Donald Trump was a true man, he would not pick a fight with and attack a defenseless woman).

The incompetent, uneducated, imbecilic, xenophobic and racist Donald Trump has admitted that he would consider the release of Meng from Canadian's Department of Justice and ignore the rulings of the Canadian Court System that is supposed to be independent and impartial if it would help him score points in his useless and dangerous Trade War with China [23]. Through his action and declarations, the incompetent, uneducated, imbecilic, xenophobic and racist Donald Trump was essentially stating that Canada under the prime-ministership of Justin Trudeau is a banana republic and colony of the United States. The United States' Department of Justice has been unable to show in clear terms that a person of average intelligence can understand, what United States law Meng Wenzhou has violated that would warrant the arrest, persecution and imprisonment of Meng Wenzhou (Where is the rule of law that the United States like to preach to the world but does not practice!). As the Chief Financial Officer of Huawei, Meng Wenzhou participated in a financial transaction with HSBC that involved Iran. The transaction took place in Hong Kong, a territory that is under the jurisdiction of China. China and the European Union do not have any restrictions on doing business with Iran. Only United

States do. Meng was arrested on the ground that "she committed fraud and conspiracy to commit fraud in order to circumvent U.S. sanctions against Iran". Meng Wenzhou was formally charged with "bank fraud, wire fraud, and conspiracies to commit bank and wire fraud" [24,25].

A number of questions can be asked and if answered impartially would prove that the arrest of Meng Wenzhou was political in nature and connected to the the useless and ill-conceived Trade War against China initiated by the incompetent, uneducated, imbecilic, xenophobic and racist Donald Trump: 1. Did Meng Wenzhou commit "bank fraud"? In the United States, under 18 U.S.C. § 1344, 'bank fraud' occurs when the perpetrator has used subterfuge or a criminal scheme to defraud in order to obtain something of value and the victim must have acted upon the subterfuge or criminal scheme and lost something of value as a result; 2. Did Meng Wenzhou commit "wire fraud"? In the United States, under 18 U.S.C. § 1343, 'wire fraud' occurs when the perpetrator uses the telephone or other electronic means, including fax equipment, computer equipment and online internet services to affect the crime of fraud; 3. Did Meng Wenzhou use subterfuge or a criminal

scheme to trick HSBC into performing an illegal act? 4. Did Meng Wenzhou commit "conspiracies to commit bank and wire fraud"? Meng Wenzhou did not use subterfuge or a criminal scheme in her dealing with HSBC; It is crystal clear that Meng Wenzhou did not commit "bank fraud and wire fraud" because in her dealing with HSBC, there is evidence showing that HSBC knew or had reason to know that Huawei through Skycom was doing business with Iran. Meng Wenzhou could not have committed "conspiracies to commit bank and wire fraud" because it is axiomatic that a conspiracy must be committed by more than one person. In this comical but tragic case, only one person has been charged, arrested, imprisoned and prosecuted. The evidence in the form of Slides, No. 6 and No. 16 shows that HSBC knew or had reasons to know that Huawei through Skycom was conducting business with Iran, Huawei had controlling interest in Skycom and that by processing Skycom funds through U.S. Banks, HSBC was violating United States Sanction against Iran [25]. HSBC could have conducted the Skycom transactions through the Clearing House Automated Transfer system (CHATS) in Hong Kong and not violate United States Sanctions Law against Iran. HSBC chose not to do that. China and the European Union

conduct business with Iran without violating United States Sanctions Law against Iran [26,27]. HSBC is the entity and not Meng Wenzhou that violated United States' Sanction Law against Iran. HSBC and not Meng Wenzhou should be the one being prosecuted by the United States Government. That Canada under the prime-ministership of the incompetent, imbecilic and clownish Justin Trudeau is being treated as a Banana Republic is an understatement. That the incompetent, imbecilic and clownish Justin Trudeau is a "neophyte" is an understatement. The Former Prime Minister of Canada, Jean Chretien have stated that "the United States played a trick on Canada by forcing Ottawa to arrest Ms. Meng, and called the extradition request an unacceptable move by the United States at the expense of Canada and its farmers and pork producers" [28].

As if Canada under the prime-ministership of incompetent, imbecilic and clownish Justin Trudeau does not have enough internal problems, the latest attack of China by Canada with respect to the Joint Declaration [8] is further evidence that the Prime Minister of Canada, Justin Trudeau is an incompetent, imbecilic and a clownish individual who lacks knowledge of world affairs, diplomatic

skills and political acumen. The Joint Declaration [8] signed by Canada under the prime-ministership of Justin Trudeau essentially states that the panel of Scientific Researchers are a bunch of imbeciles who allowed themselves to be corrupted by China and that China is a cheat. One does not deal with one of the world's pre-eminent economic and military powers by insulting it. Canada under the prime-ministership of incompetent, imbecilic and clownish Justin Trudeau (the neophyte) is paying the price for insulting China and the Chinese people. The fact that Canada under the incompetent, imbecilic and clownish Justin Trudeau (the neophyte) is struggling to cope with SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19 and has so far registered more than 24,000 deaths (still counting!) for a population of ~38 million (See Figure 2 for a comparison of the IP-10000 and DPP-10000 with other countries) is testament to the incompetence and imbecility of the Prime Minister of Canada, Justin Trudeau (Mr. Justin Trudeau! It is not rocket science. Please use your brain more than your mouth! 24,000 deaths for a population of ~38,000,000 is not acceptable!).

The United States, United Kingdom and Canada are playing dangerous political games that have cost over 590,000, 127,000

and 24,000 lives (still counting!) and trillion of dollars in their respective countries already. What are the real reasons for their attack of China? The United Kingdom and Canada are clearly lackeys of the United States and therefore do not have any choice but to kowtow and do the dirty work of the United States, as suggested by Jean Chretien, a former Prime Minister of Canada [28] (As a United States Citizen, I do feel bad that the United Kingdom and Canada are willing lackeys of the United States and are parties to my country's mischief and immoral acts). The latest actions of the United Kingdom and Canada are in line with their status as lackeys of the United States. The United Kingdom's virulence towards China with respect to Hong Kong is not only hypocritical, reckless and comical but also dangerous. It never occurred to the United States, United Kingdom and Canada that the Governor of Hong Kong was always appointed and not elected when the United Kingdom was ruling Hong Kong and there was no elected legislative body in Hong Kong. The accusation of genocide against Uighur people committed by China without any credible proof by the Government of United States, United Kingdom and Canada is the continuation of their China bashing, irrational fear of the yellow peril syndrome

and disgusting racism. The arrest and prosecution of Meng Wenzhou, the Chief Financial Officer of Huawei by the Canadian Government, instigated by the United States Government under the incompetent, imbecilic, clownish, xenophobic and racist Donald Trump has more to do with political posturing of Donald Trump than the business of justice (It is a pity that Joe Biden does not have the moral courage to say that it is wrong for the United States of America to go after Meng Wenzhou, a defenseless woman and the United States of America does not go after defenseless women. Only the incompetent, imbecilic, clownish, xenophobic and racist Donald Trump can do that!). The action of the Canadian Government of Justin Trudeau is not only hypocritical and shows clearly that Canada under the premiership of incompetent, imbecilic and clownish Justin Trudeau is a lackey of the United States but also highly hypocritical, reckless and dangerous. The action of the Canadian Government of incompetent, imbecilic and clownish Justin Trudeau has made Canada a laughing stock.

It is quite surprising that not many so-called experts and pundits have criticized the declaration of the WHO Director and the Joint Communication approved by the

Political Leaders of the United States, United Kingdom, Canada and other countries! The so-called experts and pundits, including Editors in Chiefs of scientific journals (e.g. Science, Nature, Lancet, New England Journal of Medicine etc.) have in effect thrown the Scientific Researchers who went to Wuhan, China under the bus. It can be surmised that in the future, no qualified Scientific Researchers with integrity and independence will volunteer to be despised and thrown under the bus. Are these so-called experts and pundits also stating that the panel of Scientific Researchers who went to Wuhan, China, a bunch of imbeciles? What is also quite surprising is that a self-proclaimed expert with zero knowledge in the sciences of Virology, Jamie Metl [29] has taken upon himself to convince a number of so-called experts and pundits from the United States, United Kingdom, Australia, Japan, and Europe to thrash the scientific report of the Scientific Researchers who went to Wuhan, China to investigate the origin of SARS-COV-2 and to force a new investigation "in the most systematic way possible" without China's involvement. Who the hell is Jamie Metl? Who the hell are the so-called experts and pundits whom Jamie Metl convinced to sign his letter that has more to do with science fiction than science?

Jamie Metl is writer of science fiction. He should stay in the realm of science fiction as he has zero credential to talk about real science. He can fool the average uneducated population with his science fiction writing that is more appropriate for Hollywood but not practicing Scientific Researchers. He is not a Scientific Researcher in the Science of Viruses that infect humans. He has zero knowledge about the sciences that related to SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19. According to Wikipedia, Jamie Metl has a Ph.D. degree in Southeast Asian history from Oxford University and a J.D. degree from Harvard Law School. It is not clear at all what qualifies him to discuss about the Science of Viruses that infect humans and in particular SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19. After all, that is what we are talking about.

In order to determine the origin of SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19 and whether SARS-COV-2 originated from the Wuhan Institute of Virology, the original genomic RNA sequence of SARS-COV-2 must be determined. The first RNA sequence of SARS-COV-2 was determined from a patient with the symptoms of COVID-19 around December 2019 [6,7]. The virus did not come from the Wuhan Institute of Virology. If SARS-COV-2 had originated from the

Wuhan Institute of Virology, genomic RNA sequence of SARS-COV-2 should be detectable and sequenced from within the Wuhan Institute of Virology. There is no evidence of genomic RNA sequence of SARS-COV-2 that was detectable and sequenced from within the Wuhan Institute of Virology. On the other hand, partial RNA sequence of SARS-COV-2 and antibodies that recognize SARS-COV-2 encoded proteins were detected in Italy, Spain, France and the United States prior to the detection and sequencing of full-length genomic RNA sequence of SARS-COV-2 in Wuhan, China [30-33]. There are also controversies with respect to the unexpected surge of patient visit for cough and pulmonary disease at a large US Health System in the months prior to the COVID-19 Pandemic [34] and the unusual closure of the US Army Research Unit in Fort Detrick [35]. If one wants to be really thorough scientifically, one should be investigating the records of the US Army Research Unit in Fort Detrick with complete transparency by a panel of independent Scientific Researchers. One should also investigate COVID-19 like symptoms in the United States prior to December 2019. Two individuals, Segreto, R. and Deigin, Y. published an opinion piece in the scientific journal BioEssays [36] that argues without

scientific evidence that SARS-CoV-2 could have a laboratory origin. It is not clear whether Segreto, R and Deigin, Y. did any experiments in the laboratory with their brains and hands. It is respectfully submitted that Segreto, R. and Deigin should go back to the laboratory and do some experiments with their brains and hands. If they can show scientifically that they can construct the SARS-COV-2 genome in the laboratory via chemical means and use it to infect human cells and humans resulting in COVID-19, then one would be able to take them seriously. It is not clear whether Segreto R. and Deigin would be able to perform the simplest experiments with respect to SARS-COV-2. Segreto, R. is listed as a Technical Assistant with a Ph.D. degree in the field of Mycology since March 2018 and has published a few papers (not as first or last authors) in the field of mycology and not in Viruses that infect humans or SARS-COV-2. Deigin, Y. is listed as a company executive with an MBA degree as his highest qualification with zero experience or exposure in Viruses that infect humans or SARS-COV-2. It is crystal clear that Segreto, R and Deigin, Y. [36] are self-proclaimed experts and pundits with zero experience or exposure in the science of Viruses that infect humans or SARS-COV-2.

It is quite surprising that Segreto, R. and Deigin, Y. were able to publish an opinion piece in BioEssays (Has BioEssays become Fox News, CNN and MSNBC? Is the Editor in Chief of BioEssays, Andrew Moore qualified to review papers in the field of Viruses that infect humans or SARS-COV-2? The Editor in Chief of BioEssays, Andrew Moore is listed as having a background in Molecular Biology and done some post-doctoral work at the MRC Laboratory of Molecular Biology. In other words, like many Editor in Chiefs of many Scientific Journals, including Nature and their associated Journals, the Editor in Chief of BioEssays, Andrew Moore is an ex-Post-doc who could not make it in the highly demanding and competitive world of practical scientific research and has not done any work in the laboratory with his brains and hands for a long time. It is therefore not surprising that Segreto, R. and Deigin, Y. [36] who also have no practical experience in the study of Viruses that infect humans or SARS-COV-2 were able to publish an opinion piece in BioEssays. The insinuations of Segreto, R. and Deigin, Y. which referenced another opinion piece by Cyranoski, D., published in Nature [37] (a la Fox News, CNN and MSNBC) are unscientific, reckless, dangerous, defamatory

and racist. Other arm-chair scientists who are non-practicing Scientific Researchers and do not use their brains and hands in the laboratory anymore, have also published opinion pieces in BioEssays include Sirotkin, K. and Sirotkin, D. [38]. Other self-proclaimed experts and pundits who have zero experience and are not practicing scientific researchers, including Latham, and Wilson, A.K. [39] have also propounded the idea that SARS-COV-2 may have originated from the Wuhan Institute of Virology. Rebuttals by Practicing Scientific Researchers, including Anderson, K.G. et al. [40] and Tyshkovskiy and Panchin [41] have amply refuted the unscientific, reckless, dangerous, defamatory and racist insinuations of Segreto and Deigin, Sirotkin and Sirotkin, Latham and Wilson, and others [36-39].

As alluded above, in order to prove that SARS-COV-2 might have been manufactured in the Wuhan Institute of Virology or somehow escaped to infect the human population, it must first be demonstrated that it is possible to synthesize the SARS-COV-2 genome in the laboratory and the synthesized SARS-COV-2 genome can infect not only cells in culture but also infect and cause COVID-19 in humans.

Sorotkin and Sorokin [38] proposed without scientific evidence that SARS-COV-2 might have emerged "via serial passage through an animal host or cell culture " in the laboratory setting (Are Sirotkin and Sirokin [38] talking specifically of the Wuhan Institute of Virology or any laboratories including those found in the United States). The accusation of Sirotkin and Sirotkin against the Wuhan Institute of Virology is not only outlandish but also reckless, dangerous, defamatory and racist. Are Sirotkin and Sirotkin [38] suggesting that the Scientific Researchers at the Wuhan Institute of Virology are a bunch of liars and dishonest individuals? Are Sirotkin and Sirotkin suggesting that the Scientific Researchers have committed Scientist Misconduct due to Data Falsification, Data Fabrication and Dishonest Scientific Reporting because they refuse to open their Laboratory Notebooks and Records? If so, Sirotkin and Sirotkin [38] must file an official complaint with scientific justification and not innuendos and insinuations to the Chinese Academy of Sciences and to the scientific journals that have published scientific articles from the Wuhan Institute of Virology with suspect data. Then the Scientific Researchers of the Wuhan Institute of Virology will be forced to open their Laboratory Notebooks and

Records for examination by competent Scientific Researchers and not so-called experts and pundits who cannot perform the most basic procedures in the laboratory with their brains and hands. Are Sirotkin and Sirotkin capable of working in the laboratory with their brains and hands to prove their thesis? Would they know what to do? Are they able to do the simplest routine laboratory procedures of a Virology Laboratory? Thao et al. [42] have used yeast expression system to clone and assemble synthetic full-length SARS-COV-2 genomes. However, whether these synthetic full-length SARS-COV-1 genomes can infect humans and cause COVID-19 has not been determined (Due to ethical issues, the experiments will never be performed).

The recent letter of Bloom, J.D. et al. to the Science Magazine [43] entitled "Investigate the origins of COVID-19" is the latest example of self-anointed experts and pundits with no scientific experience of working with viruses that infect humans or SARS-COV-2. The scientific qualifications to act as experts and pundits of viruses that infect humans or SARS-COV-2 of these individuals [43] are questionable and suspect. When was the last time they used their brains and hands in the laboratory? Bloom, J.D. et al. [43] provide no

scientific evidence to claim that SARS-COV-2 might have been manufactured or escaped from the Wuhan Institute of Virology. Quoting the Director of the WHO, an incompetent, a moron and a clown with zero scientific background in viruses that infect humans or SARS-COV-2 is oxymoronic. The chief scientist of the Wuhan Institute of Virology, Shi Zengli has stated that the Wuhan Institute of Virology had no SARS-COV-2 genome in its repository prior to December 30, 2019 when it received a sample from of a patient, determined its sequence and submitted the information to the WHO on Jan 11, 2020 and to Nature for publication on January 20, 2020. The three bat coronavirus sequences that the Wuhan Institute of Virology had in its repository prior to December 30, 2019 had only 80% similarity to SARS-COV-2 [44-45]. Are Bloom J.D. et al. [43] stating that the Chief Scientist of the Wuhan Institute of Virology, Shi Zengli is a liar and a cheat, and that she has committed Data Falsification, Data Fabrication and Dishonest Scientific Reporting. If so, Bloom J.D. et al. [43] should have the courage to file a Complaint with verifiable scientific evidence to the Chinese Academy of Sciences and to the Scientific Journals that have published Shi Zengli's scientific works. The actions of Bloom, J.D.

et al. and Science Magazine [43] are unscientific, reckless, dangerous, racist and defamatory to Zhi Zengli. It is hypocritical of Bloom, J.D. to write that "Finally, in this time of unfortunate anti-Asian sentiment in some countries, we note that at the beginning of the pandemic, it was Chinese doctors, scientists, and citizens who shared with the world crucial information about the spread of the virus - often at great personal cost. We should show the same determination in promoting a dispassionate science-based discourse on this but important issue". Why Bloom, J.D. et al. [43] are so concerned about the assault and killing of innocent Asian-Americans and why they do not blame and castigate the incompetent, uneducated, imbecilic, xenophobic and racist Donald Trump for insisting on calling SARS-COV-2, the "China virus" and COVID-19, the "Chinese Flu" or Kung Flu" and promoting Hydroxychloroquine, Bleach and some kind of "magic light" for the treatment of COVID-19 on national TV and to the world, and for being directly responsible for more than 590,000 deaths due to COVID-19 in the United States [13-18]. Are Bloom, J.D. and Science Magazine afraid of the incompetent, uneducated, imbecilic, xenophobic and racist Donald Trump? Do Bloom, J.D. et al. [43] assume that there will be no consequence on

picking and insulting a Chinese Scientific Researcher and the Chinese people? Are Bloom, J.D. et al. [43] stating that the Scientific Researchers who went to Wuhan, China to investigate the origin of SARS-COV-2 a bunch of imbeciles? Why Bloom, J.D. et al. [43] are not insisting on investigating the origin of SARS-COV-2 in the United States, Italy, Spain and France [30-35]. The origin of SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19 in the United States is the incompetence of the uneducated, imbecilic, xenophobic and racist Donald Trump. Even a high school student would know that. Why did Science Magazine publish the letter of Bloom, J.D. et al. [43]. Is it because the Editor of Science Magazine is as racist as the incompetent, uneducated, imbecilic, xenophobic and racist Donald Trump [14].

It is recommended that the so-called experts and pundits go back to school and study about the concepts of Virus Latency, Dormancy and Activation. In particular, they should carefully study the works of Lwoff, A., Thomson, R.I. and Coates, M.S., Armstrong C., Allen et al., and Muchmore et al. [43-53].

Is Joe Biden the "Sleepy Joe" or a hypocrite? When Joe Biden was running for the Presidency of the United States, he promised that under his watch, the Government of the

United States will do things differently. Joe Biden was nicknamed "Sleepy Joe" by the Donald Trump. If Joe Biden is not the "Sleepy Joe", then he must be a hypocrite. Through his Secretary of State, Anthony Blinken, Joe with Biden has continued, consolidated and extended the policies of the Donald Trump. Anthony Blinken is no Kissinger. He needs to go back to school to learn about World Affairs, Art of diplomacy and Art of War. The actions of the United States Government under Joe Biden towards China with respect to Hong Kong, Xinjiang and Taiwan are ill-conceived, un-strategic, idiotic, reckless, racist and dangerous (It is not clear what interests the United States are defending by its geo-political posturing's vis a vis China with respect to Hong Kong, Xinjiang and Taiwan. The increase of criminal assaults and assassinations of Chinese-Americans and Asian-Americans since Joe Biden took office is a direct consequence of Joe Biden's shameful, xenophobic and racist policy towards China, the imagined enemy (Why would criminal assaults and assassinations of Asian-Americans increase under a Biden's administration? There is blood in the hands of Joe Biden and his minions). The United States must clean its own backyard first before it looks into the backyards of others.

The United States did and is still committing genocide against the native Indian-Americans. What the United States have perpetrated against the Africans and the African-Americans is etched in the shameful and despicable history of our country (Black African-Americans are still being hounded and persecuted on a daily basis! There are more black African-Americans incarcerated than other ethnic groups in the prisons of the United States of America despite the fact that black African-Americans represent only ~13 percent of the population). Is it not etched in the shameful history of the United States of America that the black people were brought to its shores in chains? Was the United States not part of the many nations, including United Kingdom, Australia, India, Germany, France, Italy, Austria, Tsarist Russia and Japan that together humiliated, occupied and tried very hard to dismember China the way United Kingdom, a nation of less than 40 million people colonized, exploited and dismembered India with a population of 300 million (It will be very difficult for history to comprehend how United Kingdom with only 20,000 troops and civil servants in India was able to rule India with a population of 300 million! Unfortunately, the Indians do not know that they have inherited a rigged so-called democracy from its former colonial

masters! and they are still slaves of that rigged system in which a minority is able to rule a majority. That the UK have ruined the lives of millions in Africa, the Middle East and Asia is an understatement. How the citizens of the UK can sleep soundly at night is beyond imagination and comprehension. The UK must atone itself but has not! By the way, the United States of America also inherited the same rigged so-called democratic system of governance from its former colonial masters. The founders of the United States of America replaced the King of the United Kingdom with a President, the House of Commons with a House of Representatives and the House of Lords with a House of Senate. The United States of America used the English laws to subjugate the slaves, the native American-Indians, the Africans and later, the African-Americans, the Asian-Americans, the Irish-Americans and the Italian-Americans. According to the Declaration of Independence and the United States Constitution, all men and women are created equal. However, it was not until 1920 and 1965 that women and black African-Americans were able to vote respectively). That the United States is still using English laws to-day is very difficult to comprehend. That the United States had copied the rules and actions of its former colonial power is

still being felt to-day. The United States have proven to the world that it can start wars but cannot win them, and have ruined many countries and the lives of millions. The action of the United States Government under Joe Biden with respect to the scientific report of the panel of Scientific Researchers who went to Wuhan, China to investigate on the origin of SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19 is unscientific, reckless, dangerous and racist. SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19 are here already and they must be dealt with within the borders of the United States of America. Are Joe Biden and his team of so-called experts and pundits afraid that SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19 will not be contained. The signs are not good. Since Joe Biden assumed the Presidency, the United States has registered an average of over 700 deaths per day due to SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19. It is criminal for Joe Biden and his appointed civil servants to accept that 700 deaths per day due to SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19 when there are currently available procedures to prevent these deaths [56]. The effectiveness and safety of the anti-COVID-19 vaccines developed by Pfizer-BioNTech, Moderna and Johnson & Johnson are yet to be proven [22]. The apparent decrease of the number of deaths due to SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19 are not due to mass vaccination but to the

change of seasons []. Mutations of SARS-COV-2 are real dangers that will surprise us (Look at what is happening in India and Brazil!). Putting all of one's eggs in a single basket is indeed foolhardy, moronic and not strategic. We will know in about 5-6 months' time whether there will be light at the end of the tunnel. Mr. President, there is a more effective, safe way and sure way to combat SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19. It is called Isolation/Confinement, Mask Wearing, Social Distancing, Testing, Contact Tracing and Treatment (IMSTCT). The development of effective drugs that prevent the replication of SARS-COV-2 for the treatment of COVID-19 must be pursued. It is not rocket science. China and several countries have done it (India did not do it and is suffering the consequence). Be humble. Study and learn, and lives will be saved. If it had not been for the incompetent, uneducated, imbecilic, xenophobic and racist Donald Trump, 95% of the 590,000 deaths registered in the United States of America could have easily been prevented. Have we already forgotten the more than 590,000 individuals (still counting!) who have died of COVID-19? Joe Biden is urged to reconsider his policies, in particular towards China and Russia. The uncertainty with respect to the United States policy towards Taiwan under Joe Biden must

be resolved (Either, we say to the Chinese, "screw you" and declare that Taiwan is an independent country or we accept that Taiwan is part of China and stop the nonsense. Who are we kidding!) The Declaration by the United States and other countries, including United Kingdom, Canada, Australia, Netherlands and Belgium that China is committing genocide against the Uyghur people in Xinjiang without any scientific or anecdotal proof is not only hypocritical but also reckless, dangerous and racist (The United States and the United Kingdom has committed and continue to commit genocide against the people who used to live in the Chagos Archipelago in the Indian Ocean [57]. It is indeed highly hypocritical of the United Kingdom to call for investigation in the allegations of genocide in Xinjiang, China when with the connivance of the United States of America, her Majesty's government of the United Kingdom deported an entire population of indigenous people from the Chagos Archipelago in the Indian Ocean and forbid the visit of graves by their relatives [57]). Did and does the United States commit genocide against the native American-Indians? Did and does Canada commit genocide against its people of the First Nations? Did and does Australia commit

genocide against its aboriginals? Did Australia kill innocent civilians in Afghanistan? Did and does India commit genocide against the Muslims in one of its provinces, named Kashmir and Jammu? The United States of America must stop being a hypocrite (The silence and action of Joe Biden with respect to the events unfolding in Palestine and Israel that the whole world is condemning are deafening and difficult to reconcile with the stated policies of the greatest defender of human rights in the world). The United States of America must practice what it preaches to the rest of the world.

The United States has already broadcasted to the whole world that it is weak and cannot compete with China "mano a mano". The fact that the United States of America is using the "Five Eyes" plus one (United States, United Kingdom, Canada, Australia, New Zealand and Japan) and the "Quad" (United States, India, Australia and Japan) to counteract, contain, vilify and attack China signals to the whole world that the United States of America is weak and cannot stand on its own vis a vis China. The specific and exclusive banning of China from the International Space Station is a shameful act from the part of the United States of America. The

successful launch of its own Space Station named Tiangong or Heaven's Palace and the landing of its Lander and Rover named Zhurong or God of Fire and War show that the strategy of containing the rise of China with ill-thought, xenophobic and racist laws not unlike the Chinese Exclusion Act of 1882 has backfired [58,59]. It is crystal clear that China will continue to rise without the help and in spite of the United States of America (Individuals, including Marco Rubio and Chuck Schumer, many Republicans and Democrats, and so-called experts and pundits of the Joe Biden Administration who keep insulting China by insinuating that China and the Chinese people, including Chinese Students and Post-Docs steal from America, must provide evidence of what has been stolen. Otherwise, they are just a bunch of liars and racists. The targeting of Chinese Students and Post-Docs, Chinese- American Scientists and American Scientists who do collaborative scientific works with China and Chinese Scientific Researchers by Marco Rubio and the Director of the United States Federal Bureau of Investigation, Christopher Wray [60,61] is shameful, reckless, dangerous and racist. The consequence of these people's actions is obvious: The best and the brightest will stop from coming to the United States of America) and the United

States will become a laughing stock in the world. Where were Chuck Schumer, Marco Rubio and Christopher Wray when the "insurrectionists" (or terrorists) were planning to assault the United States Temple of Democracy, the Capitol. Should they not be fired for failing to protect the Temple of Western Liberal Democracy and Freedom while they were thinking that Chinese Students and Post-Docs, Chinese American Scientists and American Scientists who do collaborative scientific works with China and Chinese Scientific Researchers were our greatest enemies and deserve their utmost attention? Would Nancy Pelosi say that the attack of the United States Capitol by Donald Trump's supporters was "a beautiful sight to behold". (The United States of America must advertise to the whole world that Chinese Students and Post-Docs, and Chinese Scientific Researchers are not welcomed and will be henceforth banned from entering the United States of America. The message must be clear and straight forward! Life would be simpler in the United States of America. It would avoid resources being spent on criminal Chinese students and post-docs who lie in their visa applications.

On the contrary, in the opinion of this author, the United States of America should feel

honored that the Chinese Students want to come and study here. The United States of America must be a gracious host with respect to these honorable guests. Without that, many Chinese-Americans who have founded many successful companies would not be here but in China. It is unclear to this author why Chinese Students and Post-Docs, and Chinese Scientific Researchers want to come to the United States of America). How many Chinese-American Scientific Researchers and other American Scientific Researchers have the United States Government wrongly arrested and prosecuted? It will remain a shameful stain in our history just like the lynching of Chinese-Americans, Irish-Americans, Italian-Americans, Mexican-Americans Jewish-Americans and Black African-Americans are stains that can never be wiped clean.

It is time the United States of America adopt a truly civilized conduct worthy of the declared greatest defender of human rights and freedom and learn of the Art of Diplomacy and Art of War (It is preferable to win a battle without fighting). It is sincerely hoped that the Joe Biden Administration knows that China is not anything like the former Soviet Union, Afghanistan, Iraq, Libya and Iran. The United States of America

has just lost the war in Afghanistan. Does the United States of America have the capacity and will to conduct a useless war (cold or hot) against China (Let us not forget what happened in Vietnam and Korea!). The United States of America does not need another un-winnable war that can lead to the end of life on Earth for the obvious reasons (Both countries and Russia have enough nuclear warheads to destroy Earth several times!). When the United States of America and China work together or at the very least respect each other, the citizens of the United States of America and China, and the world will benefit.

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